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Traffic Congestion in Beirut, Lebanon

Environmental Impact, Financial Consequences, and Possible Solutions!

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ABSTRACT

In the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), Lebanon, there is a high dependency on private car use that has seriously exacerbated road traffic congestion with traffic literally coming to a complete standstill for hours, turning the daily commute to/from the city center of Beirut into an ordeal for many people. Studies to implement an efficient public transport system to alleviate this problem are underway – however, the dire political, humanitarian, economic and financial crisis Lebanon is currently facing, in combination with the corona virus (Covid-19) pandemic, has been slowing down progress in this respect.

Introduction

This article was partially written before Tuesday the 4th of August 2020 when, at 6:09 p.m. local time, a large explosion occurred at a warehouse in the Port of Beirut, Lebanon. This resulted not only in the destruction of buildings and infrastructure in a large section of Beirut, but also devastated the lives of many people who were just going about their daily lives, leaving some 200 deaths, 6,000 injured, 300,000 people homeless and an unknown number unaccounted for in its wake. With Lebanon already suffering from a serious economic and financial downward spiral since the autumn of 2019, which has led to a sharp devaluation of its national currency against the US Dollar, sky rocketing prices for food and other basic necessities, high unemployment rates, poverty, famine and fear, shortages of medical supplies and medicines, as well as having to cope with the spreading of the corona virus (Covid-19) pandemic, this was literally a blow that the country did not need nor deserve.

Reconstruction cost of the various buildings and infrastructure is currently estimated at some \$15 billion, whereas the rebuilding of the lives of many people in Beirut and beyond will take much more than just money. Lebanon cannot do this on its own, as it is highly in debt and its finances are nearly depleted. The country itself is on the brink of collapse. Assistance from the international community and financial institutions is very much needed, in order to aid this country in its endeavours to pick up the rubble, dust down the pieces and start rebuilding the various buildings and infrastructure, as well as the lives and livelihoods of its people – so that there may be hope for both Lebanon and its people!

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Public Transport Virtually Lacking

Lebanon used to have one of the most advanced public transport systems in the Middle East, with trams, buses and trains providing efficient services. However, the fraternal infighting that ripped through the material and social fabric of the country during the civil war (1975-1990), unfortunately, also laid waste to its sophisticated public transport network. Since the civil war, there has not been an efficient public transport infrastructure in place due to a lack of funds and, therefore, there is a high dependency on private car use.

High dependency on private car use

The high dependency on private car use has seriously exacerbated road traffic congestion in Lebanon, especially in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), turning the daily commute to/from the city center of Beirut into an ordeal for many people (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The daily commute to/from the city center of Beirut

The situation has also worsened over recent years, due to the influx of some 1.5 million refugees from neighboring Syria, who now make up roughly 25% of the resident population in Lebanon – this has led to an increase in road traffic levels of about 15-25% (with some 50% of the households in Lebanon owning one car, and about 25% owning at least two, there is almost one car for every two persons in the country (BLOMINVEST, 2015)). Further, road traffic congestion is also exacerbated by the fact that many roads are in a poor state of repair.

Public transport infrastructure and facilities virtually non-existent

Whatever public transport there is comes in the form of taxi, minibus and bus services. The bus services are provided either by OCFTC (Office for Railways and Public Transport), a public entity that comes under the tutelage of the Ministry of Public Works & Transport, or by a number of private bus operators. OCFTC receives a subsidy to assist in its provision of the bus services, whilst the private operators exist without any subsidy.

The minibuses operate either as communal taxis on popular routes or on a roaming basis, as do taxis – these and the bus services are not facilitated with a proper infrastructure to make them easily accessible to the public, and also lack facilities (e.g. bus stations, dedicated taxi-spots [taxi ranks] and proper scheduling) to provide an efficient and reliable public transport system – ultimately leading people to use the only reliable option: the private car.

Furthermore, the existing public transport (taxi, minibus and bus) services are not only unreliable but, in most cases, also unevenly distributed over the market. The city of Beirut, for instance, is over-served as compared to the demand, resulting in severe competition among operators, whereas other cities have a shortage of public transport services. In fact, the number of taxis and minibuses in the city of Beirut is increasing rapidly, giving rise for concern, as it has become clear that these also contribute significantly to road traffic congestion.

In a report published in 2015 (BLOMINVEST, 2015), it was noted that the number of daily motorized trips within the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), which has a population of over 2 million people, reached some 5,000,000, with about 68% of these journeys made by private car, with an occupancy rate of 1.6 persons/car (see Table 1).

Table 1. Daily motorised trips in GBA – share per transport mode (BLOMINVEST, 2015)

Greater Beirut Area (GBA)	
Population	> 2,000,000
Daily number of motorized trips	5,000,000
Share of daily number of motorized trips per transport mode	
Taxis & Minibuses	15%
Private Sector Buses	14%
OCFTC Buses	3%
Private Cars	68%

Mobility cost

Mobility cost in Lebanon is estimated to be around USD 50 cents/vehicle km or USD 42 cents/passenger km. Furthermore, the road transport sector in Lebanon is one of the largest energy consumers (27.42% of the national energy consumption). This reflects the economic burden that the road transport sector has not just on the people, but also on the national economy.

Implementation of a properly managed and efficient public transport system could address three components of mobility cost, i.e. through:

- reducing air pollution levels;
- lowering fuel consumption, resulting from a decrease in private car use; and
- reducing car ownership costs.

As regards the latter (reducing car ownership costs), of the annual household expenditure in Lebanon, transportation cost represents the third largest share (13.11% of total expenditure), after expenditure on housing (28.36%) and food (20%) – the latter may not be quite the case at this moment in time as, besides having to deal with the currently prevailing corona virus (Covid-19) pandemic, Lebanon is also faced by a very serious economic and financial crisis that has seen a sharp fall in the exchange rate of the Lebanese Pound against the US Dollar, and a sharp rise in the prices for food and other goods and

necessities, leaving many people destitute and on the verge of famine. Further, daily power outages and increased levels of unemployment are pushing the country to the verge of total collapse – a very dire situation indeed!

High Private Car Use: Road Traffic Congestion, Environment and Economy

The high private car use results in serious road traffic congestion, especially during the peak-hour periods, and also has a high impact on the environment, as well as financial consequences for the economy of Lebanon, Choueiri (2015) and Choueiri (2020).

Road traffic congestion

The World Bank estimates that some 650,000 road vehicles enter the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) on a daily basis, with 300,000 accessing the city via the northern approach from the Jounieh-Beirut highway, 200,000 via the southern approach, and 150,000 via the eastern highway – not counting the vehicles already circulating in Beirut (Rahhal, 2019).

During the morning peak-hour period (between 6:45 a.m. and 11:00 a.m.) and the evening peak-hour period (between 4:00 p.m. and 7:00 p.m.), road traffic speeds are usually very low, ranging from 30 km/h on main roads to less than 10 km/h on secondary roads, with traffic literally coming to a complete standstill for hours, which seriously increases journey times. During peak-hour periods, traffic on the northern approach to the city center alone may reach an hourly high of 7,000 vehicles; these vehicles often spend hours jammed on this north-south artery that runs along the full length of the Mediterranean coast line, connecting Beirut to the cities of Jounieh and Tripoli in the north, and Sidon and Tyre in the south.

Environmental impact

The high dependency on private car use not only causes road traffic congestion, but also has an environmental impact as regards:

- **noise:** the road traffic congestion situation is accompanied with unacceptable levels of noise, due to the high traffic density, old vehicle engines and also an excessive use of the claxon. On the main roads of the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), noise levels reaching 90-95 dB have been measured, whereas the standard level is 72 dB. The measured noise levels fall into the category that cause irritation and may well also lead to health problems.
- **air pollution:** with 25% of CO₂ emissions in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) coming from the land transport sector, which is estimated to consume about 45% of all imported fuel, the contribution of road traffic to air pollution is very significant. The proliferation of the use of badly-run engines on taxi services also greatly contributes to this. The high levels of air pollution in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), which has also become a serious deterrent to tourists to visit the city, also lead to high medical costs due to illnesses caused by the said air pollution.

Financial consequences

The cost of the road traffic congestion situation in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) to the economy of Lebanon is at least a substantial USD 2 billion a year (THE DAILY STAR, 2017). Further, the heavy traffic in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) also leads to the occurrence of a high number of road traffic accidents, with high inherent costs to the country's economy.

Road traffic congestion cost is largely attributable to time wasted in traffic jams – the adage “time is money” is true in this respect, as well as excess fuel consumption, impact on economic productivity, health problems resulting from air pollution, a higher cost of rent as people tend to live closer to their jobs, and increased vehicle operating costs. As regards the latter, vehicle operating costs also increase because of poor road conditions [Lebanon’s roads ranked 124 in terms of road quality among 138 countries, i.e. one of the worst, according to the 2016-2017 Global Competitiveness Index of the World Economic Forum (World Economic Forum, 2016)].

An Efficient and Reliable Public Transport System Urgently Needed

Studies to implement an efficient public transport system to alleviate road traffic congestion in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) are underway, as building more roads, demolishing buildings to make space for more cars, and adding more parking spaces will only exacerbate the problem. In a report for a road traffic congestion situation in the United Kingdom (LEIGH, 2016), it is noted that such measures would only provide a temporary relief until the induced demand replenishes the space available on the roads, and also that business cases to solve road traffic congestion should be developed very carefully and take into account the prevailing situation in the specific city and country in question.

In the case of Beirut, decreasing road traffic congestion by developing more roads, for instance, is not a viable option because of its urban density and terrain, with the mountains to one side, the sea to another, and a narrow coastal strip in-between. Any road development project would require either the expropriation of land or the construction of tunnels in mountains or highways over the sea, all of which would be costly options. This leaves developing an efficient public transport system as the only option.

An efficient public transport system – the only option

According to Choueiri (2014), Choueiri (2018) and Choueiri (2020), an efficient public transport system is the only option. Among the studies into implementing an efficient public transport system in Lebanon railways are looked at. In this respect, a number of routes are under focus for possible revitalization (see Figure 2):

- ***Beirut - Jounieh - Tabarja-Maameltein (- Tripoli)***: in an effort to alleviate road traffic congestion in Beirut, especially on the northern approach into the city centre, studies have been conducted to see if the situation could be alleviated by implementing railway services between Beirut and Tabarja-Maameltein, and even beyond to Tripoli, using the existing coastal railway right-of-way. If sufficient funds were to become available, it has been recommended to extend the studies also to the south of Beirut, at least to the coastal town of Jiyeh, near Sidon.
- ***Tripoli - Abboudiyeh***: the government has assigned the Council for Development and Reconstruction (CDR) of Lebanon to look into the possibility of revitalising the railway line between Tripoli and Abboudiyeh on the Lebanese/Syrian border, in coordination with the country’s Railways & Public Transport Authority (RPTA).

For the aforementioned railway lines to become a reality, it would take quite some time. However, the dire road traffic congestion situation needs to be alleviated much sooner – a temporary solution could come in the form of the Greater Beirut Urban Transport (GBUT) project.

The Greater Beirut Urban Transport (GBUT) project

The Greater Beirut Urban Transport (GBUT) project, by implementing a new Bus Rapid Transit (BRT)

system between the densely-populated Tabarja-Maameltein/Jounieh area and Beirut (see Figure 2), as well as feeder bus services to the trunk BRT system and within Beirut, is aimed at improving transport connectivity and mobility on the northern approach into the city center of Beirut. The project also includes the establishment of appropriate institutional entities for the management, operation and maintenance of this BRT system. Once effected, it would become Lebanon's first modern public transport system in decades.

Figure 2. Routes are under focus for possible revitalization.

Attracting private car users to become public transport patrons

For any public transport system to be conceptualized to accommodate a reasonable level of ridership on a given corridor, it is essential that the system specifically understands, targets and adapts itself to the current private car users. Once an objective has been established, then it can be executed through respective levels of subsidy, as well as fare and price discrimination mechanisms.

As regards implementing a public transport system, the following aspects could influence the levels of ridership: parking fees; pedestrian-only zones in the Central Business District; feeder bus networks; fare and service integration with feeder bus networks; park-and-ride facilities at stations; and level of services and amenities provided.

For attracting current private car users, the majority of whom would be middle-class professionals, to patronize the public transport system, it should be recognized that one of the key variables would be the location of stations. Also, in suburban areas, the stations would need to have adequate parking facilities, as the majority of commuters would need to park their cars at the station and then use the public transport system to commute into the city.

As for stations in Beirut, it would be very important to address the issue of transport mode transfer, as well as to consider the walking distance from the station to the Central Business District or other destinations in the city. For instance, requiring a commuter to use three modes of transport to get to his/her place of work would likely diminish ridership.

Based on the levels of ridership expected, the respective public transport system could be sized, such as regards the number of vehicles required, if there is a need for a single or double-track system, etc. This will then allow the development of a rough estimate of the relative costs of the bus and railway alternatives, including both capital and ongoing operating costs. Based on the comparative costs and other characteristics, such as the ability to attract additional patronage, contribution to urban development objectives, environmental impact, and other implications of the alternative systems, a preliminary selection of the eligible technologies could then be recommended. It is important to recognize that this would remain a preliminary recommendation until further developments of the study are completed. The intent here is to provide broad system characteristics, including vehicle travel speed, capacity and frequency, which would meet the anticipated levels of ridership.

Concluding Remarks

The high dependency on private car use in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) has seriously exacerbated road traffic congestion, turning the daily commute to/from the city center of Beirut into an ordeal for many people. Building more roads, demolishing buildings to make space for more cars, and adding more parking spaces will only make the problem worse, whereas the development of a reliable and efficient public transport system with optimal services and facilities, once in place, could well attract the patronage of many current private car users. This would alleviate road traffic congestion, as well as noise and air pollution, in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) – it would also enhance the mobility and quality of life of the people. It could also attract more visitors and tourists to Beirut, bringing both societal and economic benefits. However, for all this to become a reality, the financial support from external bodies (e.g. World Bank, the European Union (EU), the European Investment Bank (EIB) and the United Nations' Development Programme (UNDP)) would be very much needed.

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